

A LOOK AT THE CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PROFESSOR TAVAKKAL KADIROV, THE PEOPLE'S ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The life and creative work of the People's Artist of Uzbekistan, professor Tavakkal Kadirov, as an artist with his own school in the Uzbek classic khofiz (singer) art, his songs still take a strong place in the creativity of young people.*

Keywords: *popular title "Nightingale of Uzbekistan", composition art, recognition by musicologists as the owner of a unique voice.*

In ancient times, the performers of works created based on the poems of Uzbek folk music were named differently: singer, hafiz, yallachi, big singer, laparchi, interpreter, makomkhan, savtkhan, bakhshi, poet, zakir, mughanni, mutrib, yirovchi, goyanda, etc. These performers are divided into several groups. For example, *maqam* performers are called *maqamhon*, hafiz, khanda, savkhan, *doston* music performers are called bakhshi, poet, dostani, yirovchi, *popular genre* performers are called yallachi, laparchi, singer, singer. The naming of singers in this way is largely related to the variety of genres and forms of Uzbek national music. This shows that each performer has excellent experience and high level in his chosen field. Among the people, they were called "Savtkhan", "Yallachi", "Katta ashulachi", "Talqinchi", "Poet", "Bakhshi". These names indicate the performance and (professional) level of the performer. For example, it is known that a bakhshi never says maqam or a great singer never says lapar. For many centuries, poets have expressed the art of music, its performers - singers, musicians, musical instruments, the influence and power of status on the human soul, the art of dance performed with music, music in battles, in royal palaces. Just as a singer creates under the influence of a poet's poem, a poet also creates poems inspired by the performance of singers and musicians. Uzbek music creators also named some of their own tunes. For example, in Bukhara Shashmaqom there are Saqili Ashkullo, Saqili Islamkhan, Mukhammasi Mirzohakim, Mukhammasi Nasrullah, Mukhammasi Hajikhoja, while in Khorezm maqams there are Murabayni Kamil, Mukhammasi Feruz, Saqili Mirza, Saqili Muhrkhan, Feruz I, II, Savti Feruz, Saqili Niyazkhoja, Saqili Sultan and others. occurs. People's artist of Uzbekistan, professor Tavakkal Kadirov was born in 1926 in Kuva district, Fergana region. From a young age, he is interested in art and sports, his interest in art surpasses his interest in sports. At first, he learned to play the circle and gijjak (violin) from Tursunboy Karimov of Kuva, classic instrumental tunes such as "Dugok", "Segok", folk songs ("Yolgiz", "O'ltirgyu", etc.) from Gofurjon and Yakubjon Hashimov. Later, he learned the songs of Uzbek classical and modern composers from Komiljon Otaniyozov, Jorakhan Sultanov. He graduated from Fergana Music Academy (1961). (1951-1959) - artistic director at the Kuva District House of Culture, (1959-1978) - years at the Fergana Theater, (1978-1991) - soloist at the Fergana Interregional Philharmonic, (1978-1983) - director, (1991 - from 2006) was creatively active as a professor at Fergana University. Unique, juicy, sonorous and clear, extremely wide and high-range sound. Since 1955, he has worked with Jaloliddin Okhunov. From the repertoire of Fergana - examples of Tashkent music style ("Ko'qon Ushshoghi", "Tashkent Iroghi", "Tanavor", "Nasruloyi" and others), Khorezm roads ("Suvora",

"Feruz", "Segokh"), modern composers ("Toy Mubarak", Fakhriddin Sadikov: "Leave us", "Fergana before dawn", Mukhtarjon Murtazoev: "Dog'man", Komiljon Otaniyozov: "Don't die", Jorakhan Sultanov and others) and to the ghazals of classical and modern poets created by him ("O'ayyytku", Hamza poem: "Shunchamidi", Okhunjon Hakimov: "From Jamollaring", Nakhshi: "Yesterday Moon", Mirtemir: "Oynasin", Habibiy and others) songs and yallas are widely used. The performance style is characterized by the wide use of high climaxes, fluency, wide breathing, and the pronunciation of each word piece by piece. 2 television films (1963 - 1992) and a video film (1991) dedicated to his work were filmed. His performances were recorded on several gramophone records and in the audio library of the Uzteleradiokompaniya. Member of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan, holder of honorary titles "Honored Artist of Uzbekistan", "People's Artist of Uzbekistan", professor, Academician of the Turan Academy of Sciences Sultanali Mannopov, "People's Artist of Uzbekistan" Nuriddin Hamrokulov, "Honored Artist of Uzbekistan" Abdulkhali Karimov, who was the honor of our country The owner of a juicy, pleasant voice was a teacher of the late artist Israiljan Usmanov and others. Fergana Art College and one of the streets was named after Tavakkal Kadirov¹. People's artist of Uzbekistan, professor, academician of Turan Academy of Sciences Sultanali Mannopov remembers this way.

- I witnessed a strange event. Have a wedding in Andijan it the morning breakfast, the teacher took a string in his hands and started singing.

' O body, if this sad winter passes, it will be spring,
The face of the desert becomes a field of violets and tulips.
The nightingale almost moans for a reason,
How many thorns will the flower face before it opens?'

At that moment, a nightingale suddenly appeared on the apple tree, which was casting a shadow over us, and began to sing. Then a wonderful thing happened. At the climax of the teacher's song, the nightingale landed on top of the tree branch and, enraptured by the song, stayed for a few minutes without singing, then flew away as if admiring it. People who saw this incident were shocked. Yes, the great artist Tavakkal Kadirov, who was honored by the people and received the name "Nightingale of Uzbekistan", literally surprised even the nightingales. Our supervisor Tavakkal Kadirov spent his whole life singing about the country and the people. He served honestly in this place of worship, the so-called Great Threshold. Our teacher was blessed with such great happiness. Although that person is no longer with us physically, but his spirit is always with us. The teacher's second life continues in the form of his children, students, friends, especially various songs. Yes, the boundaries of human life are endless, especially in the vast expanses of the world of music, the strings of the artist's heart resonate. Famous singers and young students of our country perform the original works performed and composed by the singer today, as if they were new works.

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